

INTEGRATION OF THE NONLINEAR SCHRÖDINGER EQUATION WITH SELF-CONSISTENT SOURCE VIA INVERSE SCATTERING METHOD

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Annotation. In this work is shown that the “finite density” solution of the nonlinear Schrodinger equation with self-consistent source, can be found by the inverse scattering problem for the Dirac’s type operator.

Introduction. The nonlinear Schrödinger equation (NSE)

$$iu_t - 2\chi|u|^2 u + u_{xx} = 0, \quad \chi = \text{const}$$

is used in many areas of physics. This equation belongs to the class of equations that can be solvable using the inverse scattering method for a Dirac-type operator. This was shown in the works of V.E. Zakharov and A.B. Shabat [1], L.A. Takhtadjan and L.D. Fadeev [2], M. Ablowitz, D. Kaup, A. Newell and H. Segur [3]. The sign of the constant χ corresponds to the attraction ($\chi < 0$, focusing case) and repulsion ($\chi > 0$, defocusing case) of particles. In the focusing case the problem of a finite number of particles and their bound states has a physical meaning. In the classical limit, this is modeled by vanishing boundary value problems. In the defocusing case, interest is the problem corresponding to a gas of particles with a finite density.

In connection with the application to specific physical problems, it became necessary to consider NLS not only in the class of rapidly decreasing functions, but also in classes of functions of a special form. First, in the work of V.E.Zakharov and A.B. Shabat [5], NSE was integrated in the class of “finit dense” functions, i.e., functions for which $u(x,t) \rightarrow e^{i\alpha+2it}$, $u_x(x,t) \rightarrow 0$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$. The n-soliton solution of the NSE in the case of a finite density was found in [6].

Formulation of the problem. We consider the integration of the following system of equations

$$iu_t - 2u|u|^2 + u_{xx} = -2i \sum_{n=1}^N (\phi_{1,n}^* \psi_{2,n}^* + \phi_{2,n} \psi_{1,n}), \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_{1,n}}{\partial x} - u^* \phi_{2,n} + i\xi_n \phi_{1,n} = \frac{\partial \phi_{2,n}}{\partial x} - u \phi_{1,n} - i\xi_n \phi_{2,n} = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi_{1,n}}{\partial x} - u \psi_{2,n} - i\xi_n \psi_{1,n} = \frac{\partial \psi_{2,n}}{\partial x} - u^* \psi_{1,n} + i\xi_n \psi_{2,n} = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (3)$$

with initial value

$$u(x,0) = u_0(x), \quad (4)$$

where the bar means complex conjugation and $\xi_j, j=1,2,\dots,N$ are the eigenvalues and function $u_0(x)$ satisfy the following properties:

$$1. \int_{-\infty}^0 (1-x) |u(x,t) - \rho e^{i\alpha}| dx + \int_0^{\infty} (1+x) |u(x,t) - \rho e^{i\beta}| dx < \infty,$$

2. The equation

$$L(0)y \equiv i \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} & -\bar{u}_0(x) \\ u_0(x) & -\frac{d}{dx} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{pmatrix} = \xi \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad x \in R$$

can have N number of eigenvalues. Here, the function $\bar{u}_0(x)$ is a complex conjugation of $u_0(x)$.

We also assume that the eigenfunctions $\Phi_n = (\varphi_{1,n}, \varphi_{2,n})^T$ ($\Psi_n = (\psi_{1,n}, \psi_{2,n})^T$) corresponding to $\xi_n(t)$ this eigenvalues satisfy the following normalizing conditions

$$\det\{\Psi_k^T(s,t), \Phi_k(s,t)\} = \omega_k(t), \quad k=1,2,\dots,N, \quad (5)$$

Here $\omega_k(t), j=1,2,\dots,N$ are given and the continuous functions of t .

The main goal of this work is to study the integration of the nonlinear Schrodinger equation via inverse scattering problem in the class of $u(x,t)$ function, which is sufficiently smooth and tends to its limits rapidly enough when $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$ and satisfies the condition

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 (1-x) |u(x,t) - \rho e^{i\alpha-2i\rho^2 t}| dx + \int_0^{\infty} (1+x) |u(x,t) - \rho e^{i\beta-2i\rho^2 t}| dx + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{k=1}^2 \left| \frac{\partial^k u(x,t)}{\partial x^k} \right| dx < \infty, \quad \rho > 0. \quad (6)$$

Let the function $u(x,t)$ be a solution of equation (1), from the class of functions (5). Consider an operator with a potential $u(x,t)$ that is a solution to the problem under consideration and find the evolution from t the scattering data.

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